

Development and Characterization of Functional Cold-Extruded Pasta Using Finger Millet and Carrot Pomace

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Abstract

The present study focused on developing nutritionally enriched pasta using composite flour formulated from finger millet, pulse flour, corn flour, and carrot pomace at two different incorporation levels. Cold extrusion technology utilizing a single-screw extruder was employed for pasta preparation. Two types of pasta were developed using composite flour blends, along with one control sample. Among them, composite flour P1 (comprising 30% finger millet, 20% corn flour, 20% pulse flour, 10% semolina, and 20% carrot pomace) achieved superior sensory scores compared to both the control and the P2 formulation. Pasta prepared from P1 exhibited favourable cooking properties and enhanced nutritional quality. Nutrient analysis of the P1 pasta indicated moisture content of 7.26%, ash 1.24%, protein 18.0%, fat 0.9%, crude fibre 7.98%, dietary fibre 13.72%, and carbohydrates 68.2%. Additionally, the composite flour demonstrated higher concentrations of essential mineral calcium, iron, phosphorus, magnesium, and zinc compared to the control. The developed pasta offers a promising source of protein and minerals, contributing to improved dietary nutrition for consumers.

Key words: Composite flour, Cold Extrusion, Cooking Quality, Sensory

Introduction

The busy lives and lack of leisure time in the modern world have led us to consume ready-to-eat foods. Additionally, due to their flavour and convenience of consumption, a variety of ready-to-eat snack products appeal to children all over the world. Extrusion enables rapid processing periods, which increases the efficiency of food product production (Ding et al., 2004). Mixing, kneading, frying, and shaping are all done continuously throughout extrusion cooking. Finger millet (*Eleusine coracana*), generally referred to as ragi or nachani, In India, it is a significant staple crop. Under rain-fed circumstances, it is mostly grown in the semi-arid tropics and subtropics (Thilakarathna and Raizada, 2015). It is a significant source of vital minerals, providing calcium, phosphorus, and iron (Gopalan et al., 2000). Finger millet (*Eleusine coracana*) is a significant variety of millet. It is rich in protein fibre, Iron, calcium, phosphorus; magnesium and vitamin. In addition to being a healthy source of carbs, finger millet's non-starchy polysaccharides and dietary fiber help to enhance digestive health by reducing blood glucose, preventing hyperglycemia, and relieving constipation. Maize (*Zea mays*) is a member of the Poaceae family and is a major source of starch. It contains a good amount of starch, fat, and protein. It also contains good source of dietary fibre vitamins, and minerals, some of them are thiamine, riboflavin, niacin, calcium, magnesium, potassium, phosphorus, Zinc, and sodium (Nissar et al., 2017). Maize is a gluten-free grain with unique profile of nutrients and bioactive compounds. Many of the amino acids lysine and tryptophan, which are necessary for human nutrition, are present in maize. Pulses, which belong to the Leguminosae family and are the edible seeds of plants with pods, are grown extensively

worldwide. They are well known for energy, protein, dietary fibre, vitamins, and minerals. Pulse flour is a versatile ingredient that can be used to make a variety of food products. It has been used to create healthier snacks and confections for consumers who are health-conscious because it is believed to be healthier than wheat flour (Li et al., 2017). Carotene, fiber, pectin, and substantial levels of vitamins B1, B2, B6, and B12 are all found in carrots (*Daucus carota*), a very nutrient-dense root vegetable (Manjunatha et al., 2003). The carrot juice production process generates significant amounts of discarded pomace. This pomace is notable for its high dietary fiber content and its ability to absorb significant amounts of water. Pomace is abundant in healthy ingredients including dietary fibre and carotenoids. Thus, the study's goal is to make pasta using finger millet, pulse corn, maize flour, and carrot pomace.

Materials and Methods

1. Procurement of Raw Material

The raw materials (finger millet, corn flour, semolina, and pulse powder) were procured straight from the neighbourhood market of Agra. The materials were cleaned to remove soil and debris, were sieved through fine mesh to produce fine-quality flour.

2. Preparation of Carrot Pomace

Fresh carrots were thoroughly cleaned under running tap water to remove impurities and trimmed using knife made of stainless steel. The juice was taken out from the carrots using a kuvings juicer model no B1700 leaving behind pomace as a by-product. To preserve its quality for future use, the pomace was placed in an airtight container after being dried for four hours at 60°C in a tray dryer.

3. Composite flour

Composite flour (finger millet flour, corn flour, semolina, pulse flour and carrot pomace) in two variations were used for the development of pasta with one control.

Table 1. Preparation of composite flour in different proportions

Samples	Finger millets	Corn flour	Pulse flour	Semolina	Carrot Pomace
Control	-	-	-	100g	-
P1	30g	20g	20g	10g	20g
P2	40g	20g	20g	10g	10g

4. Preparation Method of Pasta

The composite flour served as the base for the pasta formulation, with 100 grams accurately measured for each sample. The composite flour was combined with the recommended amount of water. Mixing it for 20 minutes in the extruder's mixing chamber to ensure even distribution of moisture throughout the flour. The moistened flour was extruded through an adjustable die-equipped extruder. The rotational speed of the cutter with a sharp blade in front of the die determined the pasta's uniform length of 2 cm for each sample. The extruded pasta was dried to reduce its moisture content, ensuring shelf stability and proper texture. The processed pasta samples were placed in airtight containers to maintain quality and prevent contamination, preparing them for further analysis and testing.

5. Cold Extrusion Technology

Extrusion cooking was carried out using a 5 HP induction motor-powered single-screw extruder manufactured by G.L. Extrusion Systems Pvt. Ltd. in India. The pasta was cut at a steady 600 rpm cutter speed after being extruded through a 2 mm circular die. For further

examination, the extruded pasta was subsequently placed in low-density polyethylene (LDPE) bags after being allowed to cool to room temperature naturally through convection.

6. Proximate Analysis

Moisture, ash, crude protein, crude fat, crude fiber, dietary fiber, mineral, and total carbohydrate and Starch contents of each sample were measured using the standard procedures that were indicated for each (A.O.A.C., 2000).

7. Cooking Quality of Pasta

7.1 Swelling Index

The swelling index of cooked pasta was measured following the procedure outlined by Tudorica et al. (2002). It was calculated as the amount of water absorbed per gram of dry pasta. The cooked pasta samples were dried to a constant weight at 105°C, and the swelling index was expressed using the following formula:

$$\text{Swelling Index} = \frac{\text{Weight of cooked product} - \text{weight after drying}}{\text{Weight after drying}}$$

7.2 Optimum Cooking Time & Rehydration

The method outlined by was used to determine the cooking time AOAC, (2000). An accurately weighed 10 g sample of pasta was cooked in 250 ml of boiling distilled water, without the addition of salt, while maintaining a rolling boil. Starting at the 4-minute mark, a sample was removed every 30 seconds. The pasta was then placed between two glass plates, and the optimum cooking time was assessed as the time required for the pasta core to disappear, indicating complete cooking.

$$\text{Rehydration (\%)} = \frac{\text{weight of cooked pasta (g)} - \text{weight of uncooked pasta (g)}}{\text{Weight of uncooked pasta (g)}} \times 100$$

7.3 Cooking Loss (Gruel Loss)

Ten grams of pasta were cooked in a pan with three hundred milliliters of boiling water for the ideal cooking time in order to calculate cooking loss. To measure the amount of solids lost in the gruel, the cooking water was drained into a beaker, and 25 milliliters were pipetted out and dried by evaporation in a hot air oven set at 105°C. The AACC 16-50 method (American Association of Cereal Chemists, 2000) was used to determine the percentage of gruel loss. Three tests were performed on each sample, and the average results were published.

7.4 Amount of Water Absorbed

The cooked weight of pasta, representing the weight gain during cooking, was used to measure the amount of water absorbed, serving as an index of the pasta's swelling ability. The method described by Kamble et al. (2018) was used to boil a 10 g sample of instant pasta in 300 ml of distilled water in a beaker until rehydration was finished. The pasta was cooked, and then let to cool at room temperature for five minutes before being weighed again. In grams, the cooked weight was stated.

8. Sensory evaluation

The sensory evaluation was carried out by a panel of thirty people who used a nine-point hedonic scale to rate characteristics like appearance, colour, texture, flavour, and overall acceptability. A questionnaire to rate the particular features of the extrudate samples were given to the panellists (Diaz et al., 2015).

9. Statistical analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS software, calculating mean, standard deviation, one-way ANOVA and t-tests. The LSD test was used to identify variations in pasta samples at $P \leq 0.05$.

Results and Discussion

1. Sensory Evaluation of Pasta

The sensory evaluation of the pasta samples was conducted using a 9-point hedonic scale by semi-trained panel members at food and nutrition lab in DEI Agra. A total of 30 panellists participated in the evaluation, assessing the pasta samples based on attributes such as appearance, colour, flavour, texture, aftertaste, and overall acceptability. Significant differences were observed among the samples in sensory characteristics. The highest overall acceptability was recorded for sample P1, which comprised a blend of 30% finger millet, 20% pulse flour, 20% corn flour, 20% carrot pomace, and 10% semolina.

Table 2. Sensory Evaluation of pasta

Attributes	Control	Pasta 1	Pasta 2
Appearance	6.45 ± 0.70 ^b	7.45 ± 0.73 ^a	6.21 ± 0.16
Colour	6.45 ± 0.12 ^b	7.81 ± 0.24 ^a	6.23 ± 0.03 ^b
Flavour	6.9 ± 0.41 ^{ab}	7.3 ± 0.14 ^a	6.3 ± 0.56 ^b
Texture	6.91 ± 0.20 ^b	7.6 ± 0.07 ^a	6.43 ± 0.14 ^b
Aftertaste	6.35 ± 0.14 ^b	6.95 ± 0.12 ^a	6.13 ± 0.11 ^b
Overall Acceptability	6.75 ± 0.14 ^b	7.85 ± 0.45 ^a	6.22 ± 0.22 ^b
F value	9.38*	21.94**	2.056

Note: Values are expressed as mean ± standard deviation of three determinants. Control pasta *significant at $p \leq 0.05$. Pasta 1 is **highly significant at $p \leq 0.01$ assessed by lsd test. A indicates the highest mean value in a row. B indicates a significantly lower mean value compared to a. Means sharing the same letter is not significantly different.

Attribute	Control	Pasta 1	Pasta 2
Appearance	6.45	7.45	6.21
Colour	6.45	7.81	6.23
Flavour	6.9	7.3	6.3
Texture	6.91	7.6	6.43
Aftertaste	6.35	6.95	6.13
Overall Acceptability	6.75	7.85	6.22

Sensory Evaluation

Figure 1 Sensory Evaluation

2. Nutritional Analysis of Pasta

The result of nutritional analysis of composite flour pasta and control semolina pasta are shown in Table no 2. Non-significant ($P < 0.05$) difference level was found for Ash and Starch level. Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) level was observed in Moisture, Crude Fiber, Dietary Fiber, Soluble DF, Insoluble DF, Crude Protein, Crude Fat, Carbohydrate, Amylose, and Amylopectin. Other studies results indicating that ideal moisture content $< 10\%$ in all types of pasta for longer shelf life. Composite flour pasta (finger millets pulse based pasta) in terms of increased protein, fat fibre (both soluble and insoluble), and amylose content. These improvements in nutritional composition are well-documented in studies done by Sanjiv, P. (2019) Bertoli, A. (2020), Annamalai, A. et al. (2021) Who observed higher protein and fibre levels in alternative flour pastas, particularly those made from chickpeas, lentils, and other legumes.

Table 3. Nutritional Analysis of pasta

Nutrient (g/100g)	Control semolina pasta	Composite flour pasta (P1)	T-test value
Moisture	8.76 ± 0.15^a	7.26 ± 0.024^b	2.77 *

Ash	1.23 ± 0.15 ^a	1.24 ± 0.02 ^a	0.91
Crude protein	8.86 ± 0.05 ^a	18.05 ± 0.14 ^b	4.3 *
Crude fat	1.4 ± 0.20 ^a	0.9 ± 0.04 ^b	0.04 *
Carbohydrate	72.3 ± 1.15 ^a	68.2 ± 1.05 ^b	0.01 *
Crude fibre	1.56 ± 0.04 ^a	7.98 ± 0.10 ^b	4.3 *
Dietary fibre	3.30 ± 0.13 ^a	13.7 ± 0.05 ^b	4.3 *
Soluble Df	1.2 ± 0.12 ^a	5.2 ± 0.26 ^b	0.002 *
Insoluble Df	3.9 ± 0.22 ^a	6.9 ± 0.33 ^b	0.004 *
Starch	61.2 ± 1.04 ^a	60.2 ± 1.02 ^a	0.3
Amylose	10.3 ± 0.76 ^a	12.3 ± 0.76 ^b	0.03 *
Amylopectin	40.9 ± 0.22 ^a	38.9 ± 0.21 ^b	0.0032 *

The mean ± SD and t test of three measurements are used to display the results. Significant differences based on LSD at p<0.05 are shown by means with different superscripts a, b in the same row.

3. Mineral Analysis of Pasta

The mineral content of composite flour pasta showed significant differences compared to control semolina pasta, except for magnesium. Calcium levels were also higher in composite flour pasta (24.2±0.45) compared to semolina pasta (12.6±1.5). Iron content was notably higher in composite flour pasta (6.58±0.23) versus semolina pasta (1.22±0.05), with a highly significant difference. Other nutrients, including phosphorus, iron, sodium, potassium, zinc, and vitamin A, were also significantly higher in the composite flour pasta. The increased mineral content is likely due to the addition of millet flour and carrot pomace. These results align with previous studies by Bara (2018), Dissanayake and Jayawardena (2016), and Shukla and Srivastava (2014).

Table 4. Mineral Analysis of Pasta

Nutrient (mg)	Control semolina Pasta (mg)	Composite flour Pasta (mg)	T value
Calcium	12.6 ± 1.5 ^a	24.2 ± 0.45 ^b	0.003*
Phosphorus	134 ± 2.64 ^a	145 ± 0.17 ^b	0.01*
Magnesium	23.3 ± 4.72 ^a	28.2 ± 0.58 ^a	0.21
Iron	1.22 ± 0.05 ^a	6.58 ± 0.23 ^b	0.003*
Sodium	1.06 ± 0.1 ^a	2.51 ± 0.04 ^b	0.004*
Potassium	121 ± 3.7 ^a	134 ± 0.03 ^b	0.02*
Zinc	1.5 ± 2.64 ^a	2.5 ± 0.1 ^b	0.01*
Vitamin A	49 ± 2.64 ^a	153 ± 2.64 ^b	0.01*

The mean \pm SD of three measurements is used to display the results. Significant differences based on LSD at $p < 0.05$ are shown by means with different superscripts a, b in the same row.

4. Cooking Properties of Pasta

Composite flour pasta demonstrated significantly higher water absorption 3.47 ± 0.014 compared to semolina pasta 3.26 ± 0.01 . The cooking loss was also greater in composite flour pasta 2.21 ± 0.09 compared to semolina pasta 1.83 ± 0.04 indicating a slightly higher loss of solids during cooking. Similarly, the expansion ratio was significantly higher in composite flour pasta 2.62 ± 0.04 than in semolina pasta 2.18 ± 0.01 indicating better volume expansions during cooking. The water solubility index was marginally higher in composite flour pasta 3.47 ± 0.01 than semolina pasta 3.26 ± 0.04 . No significance difference was found in Optimal cooking time, gruel Loss, swelling Index. These results suggest that while composite flour pasta has slightly different cooking properties, it retains comparable swelling and gruel loss characteristics to traditional semolina pasta. These results are in line with previous studies by Ritika et al. (2016) and Kudake et al. (2017), which found similar results when adding defatted soy flour, oat flour, millet flour, cowpea flour, chickpea flour, and other components to pasta recipes.

Table 5. Cooking Properties of pasta

Cooking properties	Semolina pasta	Composite flour pasta	T value
Optimal cooking time (min)	7.01 ± 0.04^a	8.09 ± 0.76^a	0.133
Water absorption (%)	3.26 ± 0.01^b	3.47 ± 0.014^a	6.35*
Cooking loss (%)	1.83 ± 0.04^b	2.21 ± 0.09^a	0.009*
Gruel loss (%)	21.1 ± 0.70^a	22.1 ± 0.70^a	0.155
Swelling index (%)	2.64 ± 0.07^a	2.7 ± 2.66^a	0.97
Water solubility index (%)	3.26 ± 0.04^b	3.47 ± 0.01^a	0.99*
Expansion ratio	2.18 ± 0.01^b	2.62 ± 0.04^a	0.002*

Results are expressed as mean \pm SD of three determinants. Mean with same superscript in row show significant difference in samples critical difference at $P < 0.05$ level. As assessed by t test.

Conclusion

The study developed nutritionally enhanced pasta using composite flour composed of finger millet, pulse flour, corn flour and carrot pomace. The inclusion of Finger millet and carrot pomace improved the nutritional profile of the pasta, resulting in higher protein, dietary fibre, and mineral content compared to the control. Sensory evaluation and cooking quality tests demonstrated that the composite flour pasta was well-accepted and exhibited desirable cooking properties. This nutrient-rich pasta can serve as a valuable source of proteins, dietary fibre, and essential minerals, offering a healthier alternative to traditional pasta for health-conscious consumers.

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Conflict of interest Authors declares there is no conflict of interest in this article.

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